

Employee Engagement Mediates the Effect of Training and OCB on Bawaslu Commissioner's Performance

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this study was to ascertain the impact of the following factors on performance: 1) training; 2) Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB); 3) employee engagement; 4) OCB; 5) employee engagement on performance; 6) training; and 7) OCB on performance through employee engagement. 176 District/City Bawaslu Commissioners from East Java made up the study's population. This technique to research is quantitative. In East Java, 65 District/City Bawaslu Commissioners made up the study's sample. Purposive sampling was the method used for the sampling. The findings revealed that: 1) training had no significant effect on performance; 2) OCB has a significant effect on performance; 3) training has a significant effect on employee engagement; 4) OCB has a significant effect on employee engagement; and 5) employee engagement has a significant effect on performance. 6) Training has a significant effect on the performance through employee engagement; 7) OCB has a significant effect on performance through employee engagement. The implication of the research results shows that OCB behavior shown by being willing to follow changes has the greatest influence in improving performance.

KEYWORDS: Training, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Employee Engagement. Performance

INTRODUCTION

An organization or institution's human resources are crucial. (Muzhikov et al., 2018). Any organization that is implementing a strategy views its employees as a strategic asset. (Arslan & Roudaki, 2019). To accomplish an organization's objectives as stated in its vision and purpose, good and effective management is required. The caliber of an organization's human resources determines its performance and success. An organization can succeed through effective performance, starting with raising the standard of its people resources. (Rurkkhum & Bartlett, 2012). Training, education, providing proper compensation, motivating employees, and creating a positive and supportive work environment are just a few of the ways that HR management performance may be improved. Melayu Hasibuan S. P., (2014). Gary (2015) It has been asserted that training is the process of imparting to new or existing employees the fundamental skills necessary for them to perform their jobs. One strategy to raise the standard of the workforce's human resources is training. The findings show a strong positive correlation between training and employee performance. (Sendawula et al., 2018). According to the aforementioned experts' perspectives, it can be concluded that training is a human resource management strategy that is used to develop employees' knowledge, abilities, or attitudes in order to increase employee performance.

Additionally, if employees exhibit good organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), performance can be accomplished appropriately. Employee performance will be

influenced by commitment to the company and strong contributions. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is defined by Podsakoff et al., (2000) as voluntary activity, behavior that goes above and beyond task requirements, and behavior that contributes to organizational success.

Employee engagement, which is the degree to which a person is engaged, dedicated, and loyal to the business, superiors, work, and colleagues, is another aspect that influences performance. Employees that are inspired and engaged generally contribute more in terms of productivity (Mehta & Mehta, 2013).

The reason this study was conducted in the East Java Province's Regency/City Bawaslu is because: 1) East Java Province has the most regencies/cities in Indonesia, with a total of 38; and 2) It has the most human resources. 3) Inconsistent findings from earlier studies. 4) According to some analysts, several nations have poor employee engagement levels (Nawaz et al., 2014); (Ayu Putu Widani Sugianingrat et al., 2019).

BODY TEXT

Performance

Performance is defined as the degree of success in completing tasks and the capacity to meet established objectives. If the targeted objectives can be properly realized, performance is deemed good and successful. Gibson *et al.* (2014), Performance is a metric that can be used to compare the outcomes of the implementation of tasks and duties assigned by the organization over a specific time period and, in some

cases, can be used to assess individual performance at work or organizational performance.

Training

According Octavianus, Wungow Raymond (2018); Maharani & Nurnida (2018); Soelton & Hardiati (2017). Training is a measure used by a business to increase employee performance. This claim can serve as the foundation for the hypothesis:

H1: there is a significant effect of training on performance

Research finding Suan & Nasurdin (2014), Employee engagement is significantly impacted by training. The results showed that employee engagement and OCB were both positively impacted by training satisfaction. Highly pleased employees promote professionalism, passion, and dedication in volunteer work as well as considerate behavior on the team. Additionally, businesses must keep raising training standards in order to guarantee that employees are happy with their training. (Nawaz et al., 2014). The study found a substantial positive correlation between development, OCB directed at organizations, and OCB targeted at specific individuals. (Rahman & Chowdhuri, 2018). After that, the hypothesis can be created:

H2: there is a significant effect of OCB on performance

H3: there is a significant effect of training on Employee Engagement.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

The relationship between OCB and productivity, in-role performance, and business unit performance has been highlighted in a number of research papers on the topic (AbuKhalifeh & Som, 2013). As stated by (Dian Hafit Syaifullah et. al., 2021). Employee performance is significantly improved by organizational citizenship behavior. The following hypothesis can be developed in light of the above statement:

H4: there is a significant effect of OCB on performance.

Employee Engagement

Positive individual conduct toward the company is referred to as employee engagement. This study backs up earlier studies that show that employee engagement has a favorable and significant impact on employee performance (Dian Hafit Syaifullah et. al., 2021). Employee engagement is a stronger predictor of positive organizational performance. (Markos & Sridevi, 2010). The findings show that employee engagement has a minor mediating role in the relationship between HR policies and employee creativity (Nawaz et al., 2014). The topic of employee engagement has grown to be one that could be quite important for organizational management. According to research, investing in employee engagement activities considerably improves the business unit's

performance overall (AbuKhalifeh & Som, 2013). The following is a possible hypothesis:

H5: there is a significant effect of employee engagement on performance. The following hypothesis can be used to examine if training has an indirect impact on performance through employee engagement:

H6: There is a significant effect of training on performance through employee engagement, and investigate how employee engagement affects the indirect impact of OCB on performance. H7: there is a significant effect of OCB on performance through employee engagement.

This study employed a quantitative research methodology. A total of 176 Regency/City Bawaslu Commissioners from East Java made up the study's population. The study was carried out at the East Java Province Election Supervisory Board, which is situated in Surabaya City, East Java, Indonesia, at Jalan Tanggulangin No. 3, Keputran, Kec. Tegalsari. The Slovin formula collected samples from which 65 respondents were drawn. Purposive sampling is the sampling method. main data is the data's source. A Likert scale of 1-4 is employed as the measurement system. A questionnaire (questionnaire) and interviews were utilized as the data collection methods in this study.

Training, OCB, employee engagement, and performance were the variables used in this study. The training variable indicator corresponds to the findings of study, which included instructors, participants, materials, methods, and objectives. According to Organ, D. W., Podsakof, P. M., and Mackenzie (2006); Williems & Anderson (2009), organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) indicators include: altruism, courtesy, sportsmanship, civic virtue, conscientiousness, organizational culture and climate, personality and mood, and length of service. Trust and Integrity, Nature of the Job, Line of Sight between Individual Performance and Company Performance, Career Employee Development Opportunities, Pride About the Organization, and Team Members are the markers of employee engagement that were adapted from Kumar and Pansari (2015). The following performance markers are cited by Robbins (2006): quality, quantity, effectiveness, efficiency, independence, and job commitment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity test

Each question is valid to measure the training variable, Performance, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and Employee Engagement based on the validity test results, which indicate that each question on the variables of Training, Performance, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and Employee Engagement shows significant results with an error rate of 5% or r count is greater than r table.

Reliability Test

Table 1. Reliability Test Results of Research Instruments

No.	Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Information
1.	Training (X1)	0.876	Reliabel
2.	OCB (X2)	0.939	Reliabel
3.	Commissioner Performance (Y)	0.919	Reliabel
4.	Employee Engagement (Z)	0.927	Reliabel

The following explanation explains the reliability of each variable's value in light of Table 1:

With a Cronbach alpha value of 0.876 or higher, the training variable can be reliably measured by each of the questions. This demonstrates that if the question is posed again, the answers will be reliable.

Employee Engagement variable's Cronbach value is 0.930 or greater than 0.6, while the OCB variable's value is 0.939 or

greater. A Cronbach alpha value of 0.947 or higher is present for the Commissioner's Performance variable Overall, the variables utilized in this study passed the reliability test for each variable to be used and the validity test for each question item answered, allowing for further analysis. The Path analysis test results are shown figure 2.

Figure 1. Diagram and Path Coefficient

Path Analysis Test

Explanation:

X1.1: Instructors	X2.1: Altruism	Z1: Trust and Integrity	Y1: quality
X1.2: Participants	X2.2: Courtesy	Z2: Nature of the Job	Y2: quantity
X1.3: Materials	X2.3: Sportmanship	Z3: Line of Sight between Individual Performance and Company Performance	Y3: effectiveness
X1.4: Methods	X2.4: Sportmanship	Z4: Career Employee Development Opportunities	Y4: efficiency
X1.5: Objectives	X2.5: Conscientiousness	Z5: Pride About the Organisation	Y5: independence
	X2.6: Organizational Culture and Climate	Z6: Team Members	Y6: work commitment
	X2.7: Personality and Mood		
	X2.8: Service duration		

The route equation is as follows: Figure 1 illustrates the test of the direct and indirect impacts of the Training and OCB variables on performance.

$$Z_{\text{Employee Engagement}} = 0.416 Z_{\text{Training}} + 0.272 Z_{\text{OCB}} + \epsilon_{\text{Employee Engagement}}$$

$$Y_{\text{Performance}} = -0.321 Z_{\text{Training}} + 0.656 Z_{\text{OCB}} + 0.436 Z_{\text{Employee Engagement}} + \epsilon_{\text{Performance}}$$

Hypothesis test

Direct Effect Test

Table 2. Direct Effect Test

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O /STDEV)	P Values
Employee Engagement (Z) -> Performance (Y)	0.436	0.426	0.218	2.004	0.046
OCB (X2) -> Employee Engagement (Z)	0.532	0.532	0.158	3.374	0.001
OCB (X2) -> Performance (Y)	0.656	0.698	0.148	4.418	0.000
Pelatihan (X1) -> Employee Engagement (Z)	0.416	0.417	0.154	2.694	0.007
Pelatihan (X1) -> Performance (Y)	-0.321	-0.347	0.212	1.516	0.130

According to Table 2, there is a strong correlation between the Employee Engagement variables and the Performance variable of 0.436, or 43.6 percent, meaning that OCB has a 43.6 percent impact on Employee Engagement. The significance value, which is 0.046 or less than 0.05, demonstrates this.

The relationship between the OCB variable and the Employee Engagement variable is statistically significant and is 0.532, or 53.20 percent, meaning that the OCB has a 43.6 percent impact on Employee Engagement. The significance value, which is 0.001 or less than 0.05, demonstrates this. There is a significant effect between the

variables on the performance variable OCB of 0.656 or 65.60% which means that the OCB has an effect on the performance of 65.60%. This can be seen in the significance value which is 0.000 or less than 0.05.

There is a significant effect between the training variables on employee engagement of 0.416 or 41.60%, which means that training has an effect on employee engagement of 41.60%. This can be seen in the significance value which is 0.007 or less than 0.05.

There is no significant effect between the Training variable on the Performance variable because there is a significance value of 0.130 or greater than 0.05.

Indirect Effect Test

Table 3. Indirect Effect Test

	Indirect Effect	Sig/un sig
Training (X1) on Performance (Y) Through Employee Engagement (Z)	(0,416*0,436=0,181)	Sig.
OCB (X2) on Performance (Y) Through Employee Engagement (Z)	(0,532*0,436=0,232)	Sig.

Based on the table 3, it can be seen that:

There is a significant indirect effect between the Training variable on the Performance variable of 0.181 or 18.1% which means that the Training has an indirect effect of 18.1% which is obtained by multiplying the coefficient results between Training on Employee Engagement and Employee Engagement on performance, both of which have a significant influence value, so that the results of a significant indirect effect are obtained.

By multiplying the coefficient results between OCB on Employee Engagement and Employee Engagement on Performance, both of which have a significant influence value, the results of a significant indirect effect are obtained, there is an indirect significant effect between the OCB variable on the Commissioner's Performance variable of 0.232 or 23.2 percent, which means that OCB has an indirect effect on the performance of 23.2 percent.

Model of validity

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination, Effect of Remainder on Each Equation, and Total Coefficient of Determination.

Endogen variable	Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	Residual Influence (ρ _e)	Total Coefficient of Determination (R _t ²)
Employee Engagement (Z)	0.829	0.413	0.749
Performance (Y)	0.631	0.607	

The study's coefficient of total determination is 0.749, indicating that the model can explain 74.9 percent of the

diversity of data while additional variables not included in the model can explain the remaining data. In other words,

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training (X1) and OCB (X2) through employee engagement (Z) have a direct and indirect impact on performance to the

tune of 74.9 percent, while the remaining 25.1 percent is influenced by other variables and errors.

Effect of Path Analysis

Table 5. Effect of Path Analysis

Variable	Direct effect	in Direct effect	Total Coefficient of Determination
Employee Engagement (Z) on Performance	0,436	-	0,436
Training (X ₁) on Employee Engagement (Z)	0,416	-	0,416
OCB (X ₂) on Employee Engagement (Z)	0,532	-	0,532
Training (X ₁) on Performance (Y)	-0,321	(0,416*0,436=0,181) through Employee Engagement (Z) (Sig)	-0,140
OCB (X ₂) on Performance (Y)	0,656	(0,532*0,436=0,232) through Employee Engagement (Z) (Sig)	0,888

- a. Based on the results table 5, it can be seen that the effect of OCB (X2) on Performance (Y) has the largest total influence value among others, which is 0.888 while Training (X1) on Performance (Y) has the least total influence among other variables. The indirect effect of the OCB variable (X2) on Performance (Y) has a value of 0.232, which is greater than the indirect effect of the Training variable (X1) on the Commissioner's Performance (Y) of 0.181 and both have significant values.
- b. Effect of Training (X1) on Performance (Y)
The test results obtained by training (X1) have no significant effect on performance (Y). This means that the presence or absence of training will not affect the performance of the Regency/City Bawaslu Commissioners in East Java. If it is associated with the use of questions in the questionnaire, the results obtained on average agree. But the question can not guarantee the results will be significant. The results of this study do not support the two previous studies (Octavianus, Wungow Raymond, 2018), (Maharani & Nurnida, 2018), dan (Soelton & Hardiati, 2017) in which it is claimed that training significantly affects performance.
- c. Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (X2) on Performance (Y).
Performance is significantly impacted by organizational citizenship Behavior (OCB) (X2) (Y). In other words, Regency/City Bawaslu in East Java will perform better the greater the organizational citizenship Behavior (OCB) is. The findings of this study are consistent with studies by (Soelton & Hardiati, 2017); (Nadia Mardawati, 2021)

- d. Effect Training (X₁) on *Employee Engagement* (Z).
The results prove that there is a significant effect between Training (X1) on Employee Engagement (Z). This means that the more often the training is carried out, the better Employee Engagement is formed. These results support research conducted by (Putri et al., 2021); (Esthi, 2021) which demonstrate that training significantly affects employee engagement.
- e. Effect Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (X₂) on Employee Engagement.
The study's findings demonstrate a substantial relationship between employee engagement and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) (X2) (Z). This indicates that at the Regency/City Bawaslu in East Java, the higher the organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), the better the employee engagement. These findings back up the study that was done (Hermawan et al., 2020).
- f. Effect Employee Engagement (Z) on Performance (Y)
The results of the analysis show that there is a significant effect of Employee Engagement (Z) on Performance (Y), which means that the higher the Employee Engagement formed, the better the performance of the Regency/City Bawaslu Commissioners in East Java. These results support research Haedar et al., (2021) which shows that Employee Engagement results have no significant effect on performance.
- g. Effect Training (X₁) on Performance (Y) through Employee Engagement (Z).
The findings of the data analysis in this study demonstrate that training (X1) has a substantial impact on the

performance of the commissioners (Y) in the Regency/City Bawaslu in East Java through employee engagement (Z). Although the training has no direct impact on the Bawaslu Commissioner's performance, it may have an impact on the Regency/City Bawaslu Commissioner in East Java through employee engagement.

- h. Effect Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (X_2) on Performance (Y) through Employee Engagement (Z). The result is that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (X_2) on Performance (Y) through employee engagement (Z) has a significant effect on Regency/City Bawaslu in East Java.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings suggest that: 1) Training has no significant effect on performance; 2) OCB has a significant effect on performance; 3) Training has a significant effect on Employee Engagement; 4) OCB has a significant effect on Employee Engagement; 5) Employee Engagement has a significant effect on performance; 6) Training has a significant effect on the performance of the Commissioners through Employee Engagement; 7) OCB has a significant effect on the performance of the Commissioners through Employee Engagement.

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